

Supplementary Materials:

Lübeck, T., Arend, J. M., & Pörschmann, C.(2021). „Binaural reproduction of dummy head and spherical microphone array data - A perceptual study on the minimum required spatial resolution“. The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America, 151(1), 467–483. <https://doi.org/10.1121/10.0009277>

Tim Lübeck, 02.12.2021

1. Statistics: Listening experiment results in „RData“ format. R scripts for statistical evaluation, and PDF containing the results of the SPSS analysis.
2. Static stimuli for frontal head orientation calculated for a selection of SH orders N equalized with headphone compensation filters for Sennheiser HD600 headphones and Neumann KU100 dummy head:
Name Coding:
 - DS: order-limited starting at direct sound
 - EA: order-limited after the direct sound
 - REV: order-limited starting at the mixing time
 - „ExpX_CR1_NXX_DS_front.wav“
3. Script for generation of Fig.1 „SMA_DH_error_comparison.m“
4. Script for generation of Fig.7 „SMA_splitbrir_plot.m“ showing the splitting and recomposition of the BRIRs for the reference BRIRs as an example.

R code was tested in R Studio version 1.3.1093 with R version 4.0.3 on 02.12.2021

MATLAB code was tested with MATLAB_R2020a

Requirements for the Matlabscript:

- AKtools (https://www.ak.tu-berlin.de/menue/publications/open_research_tools/aktools/)
- SOFiA-toolbox (<https://github.com/AudioGroupCologne/SOFiA>)
- SOFA API (https://github.com/sofacoustics/API_MO)